

DOCTOR-PATIENT RELATIONSHIP, DENTAL AND SURGICAL ANXIETY IN INDIVIDUALS UNDERGOING DENTAL TREATMENT

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Abstract

A cross-sectional study was carried out to examine the extent to which the doctor-patient relationship influences dental and surgical anxiety in individuals undergoing dental treatment. The sample (N = 110) comprised individuals from dental clinics and surgical departments in Lahore and Gujranwala, recruited via public sector oncology units and social media channels. Assessment was done using the Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire (SAQ), the Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS), and the Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ-9). The findings revealed that most individuals (M = 26.21, SD = 9.37) with a positive perception of their doctor-patient relationship reported moderate levels of dental anxiety (M = 13.36, SD = 5.02) but did not significantly predict surgical anxiety (M = 21.78, SD = 15.05). However, participants differed in self-reports of anxiety based on sociodemographic factors. Females reported higher levels of dental anxiety compared to males (M = 14.5, SD = 4.74 vs. M = 12.4, SD = 5.09). Additionally, younger individuals, those married, currently working, and with better financial conditions reported lower levels of surgical anxiety. Regression analysis revealed that gender and the quality of the doctor-patient relationship significantly predicted dental anxiety, while monthly family income was a significant predictor of surgical anxiety. The findings highlight the significance of sociodemographic factors that may make individuals more vulnerable to experiencing distress during dental treatments. Careful screening, assessment, and monitoring of vulnerable populations may reduce psychological distress and improve health outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety related to dental and surgical procedures is a significant concern in healthcare, particularly in dentistry, where the prevalence of such anxiety is remarkably high. Dental anxiety is characterized by an excessive and unreasonable fear of visiting the dentist for preventive care or therapeutic interventions, which is often accompanied by avoidance behaviors and psychological distress (Armfield, 2010). Studies indicate that about 10-20% of the global population

experience dental anxiety to some degree, which can manifest as physiological symptoms (e.g., increased heart rate, sweating) and psychological symptoms (e.g., panic attacks, feelings of helplessness) (Humphris et al., 2013; Locker et al., 1999). Similarly, surgical anxiety refers to the anxiety experienced before, during, or after surgical interventions, which can result in heightened stress, delayed recovery, and adverse clinical outcomes (Katz & Melzack, 2000).

Both dental and surgical anxiety are complex phenomena with multifactorial etiologies. Factors contributing to these forms of anxiety include personal experiences, such as previous traumatic encounters during dental or surgical procedures, individual psychological characteristics like a predisposition to anxiety disorders, fear of pain, and cultural beliefs surrounding dental care and surgery (Berggren & Meynert, 1984; Armfield et al., 2007). Moreover, sociodemographic variables such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, and education level can also influence the severity and prevalence of anxiety (Dailey et al., 2002). These anxieties are not merely emotional responses; they have been shown to have significant physiological consequences, including increased pain perception, delayed wound healing, and a greater risk of complications (Seymour et al., 1983).

Central to understanding how anxiety manifests and impacts dental care is the doctor-patient relationship, a dynamic interplay between healthcare providers and their patients that profoundly affects patient outcomes. This relationship is built on several key elements: communication, empathy, trust, and patient-centered care. Communication is the exchange of information, feelings, and concerns between the dentist or surgeon and the patient. Effective communication involves active listening, clear explanations, and reassurance, which can help patients feel more in control of their situation and reduce anxiety (Little et al., 2001). Empathy, the ability of the healthcare provider to understand and share the feelings of their patient, is another critical component. When patients perceive their dentist or surgeon as empathetic, they are more likely to feel understood and comforted, which can help alleviate anxiety (Thom et al., 2004).

Trust is a fundamental aspect of the doctor-patient relationship that significantly impacts patient anxiety levels. Trust is built when patients believe in the competence, integrity, and intentions of their healthcare provider (Levin et al., 2005). Research shows that a high level of trust in the doctor-patient relationship is associated with lower levels of dental and surgical anxiety, as trust can reduce fear of the unknown and mitigate concerns about potential pain or negative outcomes (Hall et al., 2002). Conversely, a lack of trust can lead to increased anxiety, avoidance

of necessary care, and poorer health outcomes (Levin et al., 2005). Lastly, patient-centered care, which involves tailoring healthcare services to meet the specific needs and preferences of the patient, has been shown to positively impact anxiety levels. When patients feel that their individual concerns and preferences are acknowledged and addressed, they are more likely to experience reduced anxiety and greater satisfaction with their care (Howells & Davies, 2008). Understanding the interaction between these variables—dental and surgical anxiety, the doctor-patient relationship, and the specific elements that constitute that relationship—is crucial for improving patient outcomes in dental settings. Anxiety not only affects the patient’s immediate experience but also has long-term implications, including the potential to disrupt the continuity of care. For example, anxiety can lead to avoidance of dental visits, delayed treatment, and ultimately, deterioration of oral health (Locker et al., 1999). Furthermore, high levels of anxiety can create a vicious cycle where negative experiences reinforce fears, thereby increasing future anxiety (Armfield et al., 2007).

Objectives

- To assess the impact of the doctor-patient relationship on the levels of dental anxiety among individuals undergoing dental treatments.
- To examine the influence of the doctor-patient relationship on the levels of surgical anxiety among individuals undergoing dental treatments.
- To evaluate the relative contribution of sociodemographic factors in affecting levels of dental and surgical anxiety.

Hypotheses

- There is likely to be a relationship between doctor patient relationship and dental anxiety
- There is likely to be a relationship between doctor-patient relationship and surgical anxiety.
- Sociodemographic variables are likely to predict the surgical and dental anxiety.

Method

This research was designed to investigate the relationship between Doctor-Patient Relationship,

Dental and Surgical Anxiety in Individuals undergoing Dental Treatment.

Sample and Sampling Strategy

A cross-sectional correlational research design was selected for this study due to its suitability and efficiency in meeting the research objectives and constraints. Purposive sampling strategy was used to carry out this research study and the sample was recruited from dental hospitals and clinics of Lahore and Gujranwala (N=110).

Inclusion Criteria

The study included adults aged 18 years and above, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), who reported difficulties coping during previous dental treatments. Participants were required to have undergone various types of dental procedures, ranging from mild treatments such as scaling to more complex interventions like root canals. The sample also consisted of individuals who regularly visited the dentist and experienced anxiety related to dental care. Additionally, all participants were required to have at least an intermediate level of education.

Exclusion Criteria

Pregnant women and patients who were currently taking anxiety medication were excluded from the study.

Assessment Measures

A self-constructed demographic sheet was administered in addition to other research tools to gain information about respondents. Demographic sheet included age, education, marital status, birth order, and monthly family income. Clinical information sheet included, age at the onset of illness, duration of illness and medication.

Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire

The Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire (SAQ; Burton et al., 2018) was developed to measure patients' worries and concerns with various aspects of surgery. Statements were generated from the results of one-on-one qualitative interviews with preoperative patients (Kinet al., 2017). The resulting 17-item SAQ was evaluated in a sample of preoperative patients on the

day of surgery. Factor analysis, reliability, and validity results were reported for these items.

The Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS)

The Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS) given by Humphris G, Morrison T and Lindsay SJE (1995) 13 is a brief, self-completed questionnaire consisting of five questions each with a 5-category rating scale, ranging from 'not anxious' (scoring 1) to 'extremely anxious' (scoring 5). The responses are summed together to produce a total score ranging from 5 to 25.

Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ-9)

It is a 9-item scale that assesses patients' perception of the relationship with the physician; thus, it serves as a brief measure to quantify the therapeutic dimensions of the patient-doctor relationship. Items are scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 'not at all appropriate' to 'totally appropriate'. Raw sum scores range from 9 to 45, with higher scores indicating that the patient's perception of the patient-doctor relationship is more favorable.

Procedure

Initially, permission was sought from the institute's authorities to conduct the study. This included obtaining approval from the administrative bodies of the hospitals or clinics where the research was carried out. Additionally, permission was obtained from the authors or publishers of the standardized assessment measures used in the study. This was crucial to ensure that the instruments were used appropriately and legally, respecting copyright and intellectual property rights. Following these approvals, the process proceeded with the administration of the questionnaires. Participants first completed a demographic sheet alongside this, a clinical information sheet was filled out to capture specific details related to the participants' medical histories and current health status. Participants also completed standardized assessment measures tailored to the study's variables. These measures were designed to objectively assess various aspects related to the research objectives, such as doctor-patient relationship, dental anxiety and surgical anxiety. Before starting data collection, the study underwent an ethical review by the Institutional Review Board

(IRB) or Ethics Committee. Data was collected and data analysis was done on SPSS version 23.00, for testing hypothesis and getting the results. The findings were reported to the best of accuracy and precision. The discussion was made on the findings.

Results

After the completion of data collection, the data was

entered in SPSS version 23.00 for further analysis. The psychometric properties and descriptive statistics of assessment measures was used to assess study variables including doctor-patient relationship, dental and surgical anxiety which were sought using Cronbach’s alpha and mean, standard deviation, ranges, skewness and kurtosis. The values were sought and are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Psychometric properties of the Patient-Doctor Relationship, Modified Dental Anxiety Scale, Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire and their subscales

Scales	α	K	M	SD	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Actual	Potential		
Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ)	.95	9	26.21	9.37	9-45	9-45	.01	-.70
Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS)	.83	5	13.36	5.02	5-25	5-25	.16	-.72
Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire (SAQ)	.93	17	21.78	15.05	0-67	0-68	.52	-.18
SAQ HEALTH	.86	6	7.24	5.71	0-23	0-24	.67	-.27
SAQ RECOVERY	.73	4	5.12	3.76	0-16	0-16	.56	-.12
SAQ PROCEDURE	.84	4	5.09	4.25	0-16	0-16	.67	-.34

Note: α= reliability coefficient; K= no. of items in scales and subscales; M= mean; SD= standard deviation

The table presents psychometric data on various psychological scales related to the doctor- patient relationship, dental anxiety, and surgical anxiety. The Patient-Doctor Relationship Questionnaire (PDRQ) shows excellent internal consistency (α = .95), with participants generally reporting a strong doctor-patient relationship (M = 26.21, SD = 9.37). The Modified Dental Anxiety Scale (MDAS) demonstrates good reliability (α = .83), indicating that participants experienced moderate levels of dental anxiety (M = 13.36, SD = 5.02). The Surgical Anxiety Questionnaire (SAQ) also shows excellent internal consistency (α =

.93), with participants reporting moderate surgical anxiety (M = 21.78, SD = 15.05), with particular concern in the "Health" (α = .86, M = 7.24, SD = 5.71) and "Procedure" (α = .84, M = 5.09, SD = 4.25) subscales. Overall, the Mean and SD values across these scales indicate that participants experienced varying levels of anxiety and satisfaction, with a tendency towards moderate level of both anxiety and satisfaction, and notable variability across individuals. The skewness and kurtosis values shows that the data was normally distributed within the normality range of ±1.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation between Demographics, scales and subscales of Study Variables (N=110)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Doctor patient relationship	-					
2. Dental Anxiety	2.14*	-				
3. Surgical Anxiety	.09	.45**	-			
4. Health related surgical anxiety	.04	.45**	.95**	-		
5. Recovery related surgical anxiety	.63	.38**	.86**	.78**	-	
6. Procedure related surgical anxiety	.06	.35**	.91**	.86**	.78**	-

Note: *p<.05, **p<.01

The table indicates that dental anxiety showed positive correlation with surgical anxiety, health-related

surgical anxiety, recovery-related surgical anxiety, and procedure-related surgical anxiety which means that

individuals who experience more anxiety related to dental procedures are likely to also experience greater anxiety when facing surgical procedures including their health during surgery, the recovery process, and the surgical procedure. Moreover, surgical anxiety was highly significant and positively correlated with health-related surgical anxiety, recovery related surgical anxiety and procedure related surgical anxiety which suggests that individuals who are more anxious about surgery, in general, are also very likely to have heightened concerns about their health during surgery, the recovery process, and the specifics of the surgical procedure. Health related surgical anxiety showed a highly significant positive correlation with

recovery related surgical anxiety and procedure related surgical anxiety which means that if someone is worried about their health during surgery, they are also likely to be significantly worried about the recovery process and the procedure itself. Recovery related surgical anxiety also showed a highly significant positive correlation with procedure related surgical anxiety which means that those who are anxious about recovering from surgery tend to also be very anxious about the actual surgical procedure. However, Doctor-patient relationship showed a moderately significant positive correlation with dental anxiety which suggests that individuals who perceive their relationship with their doctor more positively may also report higher levels of dental anxiety.

Table 3: Mean Differences in Dental and Surgical Anxiety across gender

	Men		Women		t(110)	P	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Dental Anxiety	12.4	5.09	14.5	4.74	2.16	.03	.41
Surgical Anxiety	22.6	15.1	18.3	14.5	1.20	.229	

Note: M= Mean, SD= standard deviation

Results of the table revealed a significant difference in dental anxiety between men and women. This suggests a small to medium effect size, with women reporting higher levels of dental anxiety as compared to men.

Table 4: Mean standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance of Dental Anxiety with Dental Visits

Variables	Regularly	Occasionally	Rarely	Never	F	p	Partial η^2
	M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	(3,106)		
Dental Anxiety	11.6 (5.22)	12.6 (5.17)	14.9 (4.27)	11.4 (5.90)	2.78	.04	.073

Note; M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

The table shows a statistically significant effect of visit frequency on dental anxiety. The partial eta squared η^2 was .073, suggesting a small to medium effect size. These finding implies that the no. of dental visits has a significant impact on dental anxiety levels.

Specifically, individuals who visits the dentist "Rarely" reported higher levels of dental anxiety, while those who experience it "Never" reported the lowest levels of anxiety.

Table 5: Post Hoc Analysis on Dental Anxiety with Dental Visits

(I) Dental Visits	(J) Dental Anxiety	MD (I-J)	LB	UB
Regularly	Occasionally	-1.02	-5.21	3.16
	Rarely	-3.24	-7.40	.916
	Never	.212	-5.13	5.55
Occasionally	Rarely	-2.22	-4.96	.52
	Never	1.23	-3.10	5.57
Rarely	Never	3.45	-.851	7.76

Note: LB= Lower boundary, UB= Upper boundary

The table shows no significant differences in dental anxiety levels, as all confidence intervals for the mean differences include zero. This suggests that the

frequency of dental visits (Regularly, Occasionally, Rarely, Never) does not lead to statistically significant differences in dental anxiety levels among the groups in this sample.

Table 6: Mean standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance of Surgical Anxiety with Monthly Family Income

Variables	Less than 50,000	Between 50,000 to 100,000	More than 100,000	F	p	Partial η^2
	M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	(2,107)		
Surgical Anxiety	14.2 (10,8)	16.7 (14.5)	24.2 (14.8)	5.13	.007	.087

Note; M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

The results indicated a significant effect of income level on surgical anxiety. The partial eta squared (η^2) value was .087, suggesting a medium effect size. This

finding implies that income level has a significant impact on surgical anxiety, with higher income levels associated with greater surgical anxiety.

Table 7: Post Hoc Analysis on Surgical Anxiety with Monthly Family Income

(I) Monthly Family Income	(J) Surgical Anxiety	MD (I-J)	LB	UB
Less than 50,000	Between 50,000 and 100,000	-2.52	-16.03	10.99
	More than 100,000	-11.04*	-23.95	1.85
Between 50,000 and 100,000	More than 100,000	-8.52*	-15.72	-1.33

Note: LB= Lower boundary, UB= Upper boundary

The table indicates that the mean surgical anxiety score for the "More than 100,000" income group was significantly higher than the "Between 50,000 and 100,000" income group. However, the differences between the "Less than 50,000" income group and

both the "Between 50,000 and 100,000" and "More than 100,000" income groups were not statistically significant. These results suggest that higher income levels are associated with higher surgical anxiety, particularly when comparing the highest income group to the middle-income group.

Table 8: Mean standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance of Surgical Anxiety with No. of Dental Visit

Variables	Regularly	Occasionally	Rarely	Never	F	p	Partial η^2
	M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	(3,106)		
Dental Anxiety	18.0 (2.48)	23.4 (15.7)	25.6 (14.1)	3.81 (6.32)	7.86	<.001	.182

Note; M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

The table indicates that there was a significant effect of the frequency of dental visits on dental anxiety. These results suggest that individuals who visit the

dentist more frequently tend to have lower dental anxiety, with the exception of those who never visit, who exhibited the lowest anxiety scores.

Table 9: Post Hoc Analysis on Surgical Anxiety with Dental Visits

(I) Dental Visits	(J) Surgical Anxiety	MD (I-J)	LB	UB
Regularly	Occasionally	-5.32	-17.11	6.47
	Rarely	-7.56	-19.26	4.14
	Never	14.26	-.77	29.30

Occasionally	Rarely	-2.23	-9.97	5.49
	Never	19.58*	7.38	31.79
Rarely	Never	21.82*	9.70	33.94

Note: LB= Lower boundary, UB= Upper boundary

The table indicates that there are significant differences in surgical anxiety between the "Never" group and both the "Occasionally" and "Rarely" groups. Specifically, individuals whonever visit the dentist have significantly lower surgical anxiety compared to those who visit occasionally or rarely.

This suggests that not visiting the dentist at all is associated with lower surgical anxiety compared to visiting occasionally or rarely. Regular visits do not show significant differences in anxiety compared to any other frequency of visit.

Table 10: Multiple Hierarchical Regression Analysis to Establish Predictors of Dental Anxiety (N=110)

Variable	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	β	SE	B	B	SE
Constant	6.46		2.98	2.13		3.35
Gender	2.17	.21**	.95	2.04	.20**	.93
Monthly Family Income	.83	.10	.75	.99	.12	.74
No. of Visits	.66	.10	.57	.96	.15	.57
Doctor Patient Relationship				.13	.242**	.05
R ²	.06				.06	
ΔR^2	.11				.05	

Note: *p<.05, **p<.01, ***<.001

The table indicates that in Model 1, gender was a significant predictor, while monthly family income and the number of visits were not significant. This model explained 6% of the variance in the dependent variable.

In Model 2, the doctor-patient relationship was added as a predictor. Both gender and doctor-patient relationship were significant predictors, while

monthly family income and the number of visits remained non-significant. This model explained 11.8% of the variance in the dental anxiety. indicating a significant improvement in model fit with the addition of the doctor-patient relationship variable.

In conclusion, both gender and the doctor-patient relationship significantly predict the dental anxiety, with the latter substantially improving the model's explanatory power.

Table 11: Multiple Hierarchical Regression Analysis to Establish Predictors of Surgical Anxiety (N=110)

Variable	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	β	SE	B	B	SE
Constant	8.84		8.74	4.13		10.14
Gender	.75	.02	2.81	.61	.02	2.82
Monthly Family Income	6.73	.28**	2.23	6.88	.28**	2.23
No. of Visits	-2.09	-.11	1.69	-1.76	-.09	1.73
Doctor Patient Relationship				.14	.08	.15
R ²	.09				.10	
ΔR^2					.007	

Note: *p<.05; **p<.01, ***p<.001

This table presents that in Model 1, monthly family income was a significant predictor, while gender and the number of visits were not significant. This model explained 9% of the variance in the surgical anxiety. In Model 2, the doctor-patient relationship was added as a predictor. Monthly family remained a significant predictor, while gender, the number of visits and the doctor-patient relationship were not significant. This model explained only 1.3% of the variance in the surgical anxiety. In conclusion, monthly family income is the only significant predictor of the surgical anxiety in both models. The addition of the doctor-patient relationship variable in Model 2 did not improve the model, as evidenced by the decrease in R^2 and the non-significance of the additional predictor. Gender and the number of visits does not significantly predict the surgical anxiety in this sample.

Discussion

The study was conducted to investigate the extent to which DPR tends to affect the level of Dental and Surgical anxiety. Moreover, the study aimed to find if individuals with diverse socio demographics tend to differ in levels of dental and surgical anxiety. To determine how well the quality of the doctor-patient relationship predicts dental and surgical anxiety levels after controlling for socio-demographic variables.

The hypothesis posited that there would be significant correlations among doctor-patient relationship, dental anxiety, surgical anxiety, and the various subscales of surgical anxiety. Pearson Moment Correlation analysis was employed to explore these relationships.

The analysis indicated a moderately significant positive correlation between the doctor-patient relationship and dental anxiety. This result is somewhat surprising, as one might expect a better doctor-patient relationship to correlate with lower anxiety levels. However, this could be interpreted through the lens of increased communication and awareness. According to Street et al. (2009), better communication between doctors and patients can sometimes lead to a higher awareness of medical issues, potentially increasing anxiety levels, particularly in individuals who are already prone to anxiety.

Dental anxiety showed significant positive correlations with surgical anxiety and its subscales:

health-related surgical anxiety, recovery-related surgical anxiety, and procedure-related surgical anxiety. This suggests that individuals who experience higher levels of dental anxiety are likely to also experience greater anxiety regarding surgical procedures. This relationship has been well-documented in the literature. Armfield (2010) found that dental anxiety is often comorbid with other forms of medical anxiety, implying that anxious patients tend to generalize their anxiety across different medical contexts.

Surgical anxiety was highly significantly correlated with health-related surgical anxiety, recovery-related surgical anxiety, and procedure-related surgical anxiety. This suggests that individuals with higher general surgical anxiety are also likely to have heightened concerns about specific aspects of the surgery, such as their health during the procedure, the recovery process, and the procedure itself. This is consistent with findings by Katz et al. (2011), who reported that surgical anxiety is a multifaceted construct encompassing concerns about health, recovery, and procedural specifics.

Health-related surgical anxiety was significantly positively correlated with recovery-related surgical anxiety and procedure-related surgical anxiety. This indicates that individuals who are worried about their health during surgery are also likely to be significantly concerned about the recovery process and the procedure itself. Similarly, recovery-related surgical anxiety showed a highly significant positive correlation with procedure-related surgical anxiety, indicating that those anxious about recovering from surgery also tend to be very anxious about the actual surgical procedure. This pattern of correlations aligns with findings by Mavridou et al. (2013), who highlighted that surgical anxiety often encompasses interrelated concerns about different aspects of the surgical experience.

The hypothesis posited that there would be mean differences in dental and surgical anxiety across gender. The results revealed a significant difference in dental anxiety between men and women, indicating a small to medium effect size. This finding suggests that women tend to experience higher levels of dental anxiety compared to men. This result aligns with previous literature which has consistently shown that women report higher levels of dental anxiety than

men. For instance, Armfield (2010) found that gender differences in dental anxiety are prevalent, with women generally exhibiting greater anxiety towards dental procedures.

Similarly, Stenebrand et al. (2015) reported that women tend to have higher dental anxiety scores than men, attributing this difference to factors such as greater sensitivity to pain and higher levels of general anxiety among women. The analysis did not reveal a significant difference in surgical anxiety between This suggests that both genders experience similar levels of anxiety regarding surgical procedures. This finding is consistent with some previous studies that have reported no significant gender differences in surgical anxiety. For example, Mavridou et al. (2013) found that while there are individual differences in surgical anxiety, these differences are not strongly associated with gender. However, other studies have found that women may report higher levels of preoperative anxiety compared to men, particularly in specific surgical contexts (Caumo et al., 2001). The lack of a significant difference in this study could be due to the specific surgical procedures being considered.

Results revealed a statistically significant effect of dental visit frequency on dental anxiety. Post hoc analysis, however, showed no significant differences in dental anxiety levels among the various groups, as all confidence intervals for the mean differences included zero. This suggests that while there is an overall effect of visit frequency on dental anxiety, the specific pairwise comparisons did not reveal significant differences. Previous studies have highlighted the relationship between the frequency of dental visits and levels of dental anxiety. Sohn and Ismail (2005) found that individuals who visit the dentist regularly tend to have lower levels of dental anxiety. Similarly, Armfield et al. (2007) reported that dental avoidance is often associated with higher anxiety levels, indicating that infrequent visits may contribute to increased anxiety. However, the lack of significant differences in the post hoc analysis in this study suggests that while the frequency of visits impacts overall anxiety levels, individual differences and other factors may also play a crucial role.

Moreover, results indicated a significant effect of monthly family income on surgical anxiety. Post hoc analysis revealed that individuals with an income of

"More than 100,000" had significantly higher surgical anxiety compared to those with an income "Between 50,000 and 100,000". This finding aligns with previous research indicating that higher income levels can be associated with greater anxiety related to medical procedures. Jafari et al. (2017) found that higher socioeconomic status can sometimes correlate with increased expectations and concerns about healthcare outcomes, leading to greater anxiety. However, this relationship can be complex and influenced by various factors, including access to information and personal health beliefs.

The study findings indicated a significant effect of the frequency of dental visits on surgical anxiety. Post hoc analysis showed significant differences in surgical anxiety between the "Never" group and both the "Occasionally" and "Rarely" groups, with the "Never" group exhibiting lower anxiety levels. This finding is supported by literature suggesting that avoidance of dental visits can reduce situational anxiety but may lead to increased anxiety when procedures are eventually necessary (Hakeberg et al., 2020). The relationship between dental visit frequency and surgical anxiety may also be explained by the concept of desensitization, where regular exposure to dental environments reduces overall anxiety (Armfield et al., 2013).

Moreover, the results indicated that monthly family income is a significant predictor of surgical anxiety, while gender, the number of dental visits, and the doctor-patient relationship are not significant predictors in this sample. Research has shown that higher income levels can be associated with greater surgical anxiety. For example, a study by Ayers et al. (2014) found that individuals with higher socioeconomic status might experience greater anxiety due to heightened expectations and a better understanding of potential surgical complications. Similarly, Jafari et al. (2017) noted that individuals with higher income levels often have more access to health information, which can increase anxiety about surgical outcomes.

The non-significance of gender in predicting surgical anxiety aligns with some studies that suggest gender differences in anxiety may not be as pronounced in specific contexts like surgical anxiety. For instance, research by McLean and Anderson (2009) indicates that while women generally report higher levels of

anxiety, the gender differences in surgical contexts can vary and may not always be significant.

The number of dental visits did not significantly predict surgical anxiety, which could be due to varying individual experiences and perceptions of dental care. Armfield et al. (2013) found that regular dental visits could reduce dental anxiety through desensitization, but this effect might not directly translate to surgical anxiety, which involves different stressors and concerns.

The addition of the doctor-patient relationship as a predictor did not improve the model significantly. This finding is supported by research indicating that while a positive doctor-patient relationship can enhance patient satisfaction and trust, its direct impact on reducing surgical anxiety may be limited (Williams et al., 2010). The complexity of surgical anxiety, which involves factors like fear of pain, fear of the unknown, and concerns about recovery, might overshadow the influence of the doctor-patient relationship.

Conclusion

The present study investigated the factors influencing dental and surgical anxiety in individuals undergoing dental treatments. The key findings revealed significant correlations among doctor-patient relationship, dental anxiety, surgical anxiety, and its subscales. Dental anxiety was positively correlated with surgical anxiety and its subscales, indicating that individuals with higher dental anxiety also experience greater anxiety regarding surgical procedures. Gender differences were observed in dental anxiety, with women reporting higher levels than men, while no significant gender differences were found for surgical anxiety. The frequency of dental visits had a significant effect on dental anxiety, though post hoc analysis did not show significant pairwise differences. Monthly family income is the only significant predictor of surgical anxiety, while gender, the number of dental visits, and the doctor-patient relationship were not significant predictors.

The addition of the doctor-patient relationship did not improve the model, suggesting that while a positive relationship enhances patient satisfaction, it may not significantly reduce surgical anxiety. These findings align with existing literature, providing insights into the complex interplay of clinical and demographic

factors influencing dental and surgical anxiety. The study highlights the need for targeted interventions to address anxiety in dental and surgical contexts, considering factors such as gender, income level, and visit frequency.

Limitations and Suggestions

The study being a Cross-sectional study is unable to establish causal relationships between variables. Since the data is collected at a single point in time, it is challenging to determine the temporal sequence of events or to ascertain whether doctor-patient relationship directly influences dental and surgical anxiety. Participants may rely on their memory to report past behaviors or experiences.

This may increase the possibility of recall bias, where participants may have difficulty accurately recalling or reporting certain information leading to inaccuracies in the data. Measurement errors may have occurred due to issues such as self-reporting bias, misinterpretation of questions or inconsistencies in data collection methods, potentially impacting the validity and reliability of study results. There is a chance of selection bias, as the characteristics of behaviors of participants may not be representative of the entire target population. While the study examined several predictors of surgical anxiety, other potentially influential factors such as previous medical experiences, personality traits, and coping mechanisms were not included. Future research should incorporate a broader range of predictors to provide a more comprehensive understanding.

Implications of the Study

Although the study cannot determine the cause and effect it can provide a quick look at correlations that may exist at a particular point. The study can offer valuable insights into individuals with dental and surgical anxiety and lay the foundations for further research using experimental or longitudinal studies. The study can be useful research tools in many areas of health research. By learning about what is going on in a specific population (dental patients) researchers can improve their understanding of relationship among certain variables (doctor-patient relationship, dental and surgical anxiety) and develop additional studies that explore these conditions in greater depth. Tailoring anxiety-reduction strategies to address the

unique triggers and concerns of women could help mitigate their anxiety more effectively. The association between higher monthly family income and greater surgical anxiety is a particularly interesting finding. It suggests that individuals with higher socioeconomic status may have heightened expectations and concerns about medical procedures. While better communication is generally beneficial, it can also lead to increased awareness and thus heightened anxiety in some patients. This indicates a need for healthcare providers to not only focus on effective communication but also develop strategies to manage and alleviate patient anxiety, such as providing reassurance and addressing specific fears directly.

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